

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERACTIVE GAMES IN INCREASING STUDENT SPEECH COMPETENCE

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Annotation

This article pays special attention to the development of skills and abilities specific to speech competence in mother tongue education in secondary schools. It is emphasized that a new approach to the topic using interactive methods leads to a thorough mastery of theoretical knowledge.

Keywords: Information technology, empathy, communicative, interactive, perceptive, verbal competence.

In recent years, special attention has been paid to the competence of oral communication in mother tongue education. In communication, verbal competence is seen as a manifestation of competence. Therefore, secondary school students should have, first of all, verbal competence not only in mastering their mother tongue, but also in mastering other subjects.

Verbal competence can be viewed as a perfect expression of the originally acquired knowledge. That is:

- a) be able to think independently;
- b) be able to express their ideas fluently, clearly, concisely and succinctly in their native language;
- c) speaking a literary language;
- d) thorough mastery of written and oral literacy;
- e) knowledge of foreign languages, etc.

As Utkir Hoshimov wrote, "The more languages you know, the better. But a person thinks in his mother tongue, dreams in his mother tongue, cries in his mother tongue ... Before his death he misses his mother in his mother tongue ..." [3]

Today, Uzbekistan is rising to a new, higher stage of development on the basis of the main principle "From national revival to national progress." It is no coincidence that the importance of the Uzbek language in this process has reached new heights. In particular, important issues such as the international role and prestige of our native language, the prospects of its relations with other languages, ensuring in-depth study of foreign languages, information and communication technologies for the younger generation, and even the creation of computer programs in Uzbek were on the agenda. these processes are still being carried out consistently today.

The language is not only the means of communication, but it is the great resource which is carried on the knowledge to the next descendent and made the emotional-esthetic feelings. [6]

There is a saying among our people: "Mother tongue is the soul of the nation." Language is the mirror of the nation, the source of its pride and thinking. As Abdullah Avloni writes: "The mirror life of every nation is language and literature, which shows its existence in the world. To lose the national language is to lose the spirit of the nation." [10] Therefore, before the independence of our country in 1988, the Uzbek intelligentsia fought hard to restore the rights of our language and bring it to the level of the state language. Today, every state policy aimed at the further development of our native language and the preservation of its purity will lead our national language to increase the attitude and respect of the next generation to our native language. In this regard, Professor N.Ulukov also has the following views: "It is clear that the mother tongue is the foundation of human existence, the cornerstone. Man is alive with his mother tongue. Therefore, the formation of linguistic competence in students of schools, academic lyceums and colleges, universities, should begin, first of all, with the teaching of the sacredness of the mother tongue, and develop it according to the age of the student. [7]

In this regard, it should be noted that in general education schools, special attention should be paid to the development of skills and abilities specific to speech competence.

At present, the involvement of secondary school students in the active process of teaching is a serious issue, and its positive implementation depends on the extent to which they master their native language. For example, without a perfect knowledge of one's mother tongue, it is impossible to master any foreign language or IT (Information technology), which is one of the main educational requirements of our time.

In this regard, the book "The use of learning situations in foreign language lessons" reads: "In the process of teaching foreign languages, students need to work independently and creatively apply the knowledge, skills and abilities they have acquired in new situations of communication. [5]

Or IT above What can we associate with the word?

- During communication (social networks, messengers, e-mail, chat ...);
- when receiving information (messages, weather information ...);
- in information processing (programs that perform mathematical operations, graphics, video, writing ...);
- in the process of reading (e-books, interactive lessons, manuals ...);
- on vacation (movies, music, games ...). [11]

So our lives are connected with that word.

It is obvious that it is necessary not only to integrate issues related to speech communication with other disciplines of education, but also to study their relationship with current networks of today.

Therefore, in secondary schools, not only attention to the process of speech communication of students, but also strict control should be the main focus of mother tongue education. Otherwise, conflicts and quarrels between people also arise, first of all, through their inability to understand each other in the process of communication or their inability to explain the situation well. Or conversely, the resolution of disputes and conflicts can also be resolved through dialogue.

Human understanding of each other is a complex process related to the field of cognition, and understanding each other is a complex process related to their field of thinking. A person who understands the other person correctly is considered to be able to enter his or her emotional state. That is, it develops empathy - the ability to understand someone's emotional experiences. Only a highly conscious, cultured, "seeing a lot" can understand others correctly and stand in their place. [1]

Each person has his own certain moral and ethical principles that should be laid down in school and student years. [9]

Today, as a "teacher is a lifelong actor on the board," he must be able to understand the feelings of his students, who are always watching him and feel the need to communicate directly, as a highly conscious, cultured and "seeing a lot" person. Only then will he be recognized as a highly empathetic teacher.

The following aspects should be listed as components of verbal communication:

- a) communicative - the transmission of information;
- b) interactive - interaction;
- c) perceptive - joint perception.

Deficiencies can be observed in all three of the above stages of mother tongue education. If we take the communicative process as the first stage of communication, when the teacher explains any topic, he first of all sets the communicative (information) goal. And requires interactive actions (collaborative action) from students. Because, as they say, "the fight comes from both hands", in order to achieve the result, both the educator and the learner who are communicating must work together. The teacher addresses the students with various questions and thereby evaluates them accordingly. Most students are active in this regard, but there are some students for whom it is extremely difficult to answer with a show of hands in class. The compulsively erect learner proves to be incapable of speaking at the communicative stage.

Or let's say that both parties acted together (interactively), but did not understand the idea together, did not understand the essence (that is, in quotes, one comes from the mountain and the other from the garden), in which case the communication is perceptual. degrades in terms of

This indicates that the student is not mastering the lesson well. If these aspects are neglected in the communication process, the result will be misunderstanding. This, of course, leads to irrationality, misunderstandings and a number of other negative consequences.

Therefore, any thoughtless speech can certainly lead to illogicality. About this Alisher Navoi:

Do not utter a word until it is cooked in your heart
Whatever you have in mind,

He said.

In the search for solutions to these problems, interactive methods of teaching on the principle of transition from traditional to non-traditional answer "labbay".

Inter consists of the English prefix "inter", which literally means interaction, direction. Here, the word inter has a wide range of meanings of influence, action, direction on an international scale. As for the term interactive, it means "interactive", ie the activity of the movement on a large international scale. The Latin word inter means internal potential force. [2]

Interactive methods in mother tongue lessons serve to develop students' independent and creative thinking, to express their thoughts fluently, correctly and flawlessly in oral and written forms in accordance with the speech situation, to improve the ability to understand the product of others' thinking. The main goal in this direction is to develop students' communicative competence.

In teaching the native language, the teacher should pay special attention not only to the grammatical structure, rules and definitions, the acquisition of theoretical knowledge, but also to use its rich potential to express accurate and fluent ideas, to improve language skills based on acquired knowledge. In order for a person to acquire knowledge of a language, it must become a skill and be reflected in the process of communication. Otherwise, the parable of the donkey with the book on it will remain useless. [4]

The article gives the opinions about the phonetic peculiarities of the speech, emotional — expressive function of artistic literature and phonopoetics means of poems. Every linguopoetics analyzes demand to pay attention to the figure and meaning relation. [5] Because, in the bottom of artistic texts form there is lead the meaning. The upper meaning and low meaning are retold. In the result the assimilation of the figure and meaning of artistic text are created. As long as the student is not able to re-discover the acquired knowledge, it is necessary to make the child aware that the information that enters his mind will still remain with the teacher. When this information can be passed on to peers as the teacher says, then it can be said that the information is truly mastered. At the same time, taking turns recommending students for the role of teacher will help them to develop their scientific potential, take a responsible approach to the lesson and, most importantly, master the subject. Juber has an idea: "Teaching means reading twice." [8] Now the student is very worried about being confused in front of his peers, not being able to find answers to his questions, and forgetting the opinion he is giving. Therefore, in preparing for the topic, they take a different approach than before. For the rest of the students, the ideas expressed by their peers seem interesting, engaging, and to a certain extent easier to master. To do this, it is enough to organize a game of students called "Teacher-teacher" in childhood on the basis of certain mastered topics under the supervision of a real teacher in the classroom. The difference between a game they played as a child and a game they played when they were young was when they wanted to act on each other's "instructions", and on the basis of a specially prepared lesson schedule, most importantly, they were naturally involved in each other's "instructions". For example:

1. The "teacher" (it is correct to give the identity of this student in parentheses) is prepared on the topic of a **colloquial sentence** and first tells the theoretical information about it to his peers. Draws the following diagrams on the board on the topic.

- 1) M: "K". M: "K?" M: "K!";
- 2) M: "K", - m. M: "K?" - m. M: "K!" - m.;
- 3) "K", - m. "K?" - m. "K!" - m.;
- 4) "K, - m, - k". "K, - m, - k?" "K, - m, - k!"

A well-prepared "teacher" is happy that he can draw it correctly, and his self-confidence doubles.

To the questions asked by his peers about the punctuation in this drawing in special places, he now gives explanations with examples and thus clarifies the reasons.

- 1) M: "K". M: "K?" M: "K!";

Amir Temur said: "Power is in justice."

The old man said, "Whose son are you?"

My mother said: "Come home quickly!" ...

It is obvious that through such questions and answers, imagination, perception, thinking develops widely. In fact, question and answer is a means of communication between the speaker and the listener. In it, both sides must approach with equal responsibility. No one should be indifferent to the fact that in the course of the lesson, the question of the "teacher" is answered with a number of facts, arguments, interesting facts.

The rest of the students rate the "teacher" based on the friend's readiness and ability to communicate. The "teacher" tries not to make up for the shortcomings of his friend. Organizing mother tongue education by enriching it with such interactive methods eliminates the feeling of boredom of uniformity. Enhances the effectiveness of lesson preparation in all aspects. This is because the listening students also prepare a variety of questions to test how well the "teacher" friend is prepared for the lesson . This means that this way of playing encourages everyone to be active.

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